

Generational Differences on Intra-Personal Management: An Exploration of Generation Gap

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Abstract:- Intergenerational division and disparity have always been part of human culture and is a complex concern between youth and their elders due to various factors like the technological advancements, perceptual differences, personal relations perspectives and cultural variations etc. in which the personal relations factor had more influence on the enhancement of children's intrapersonal management skills. But there is scant focus on intrapersonal management all these years which had its influence and impact on the younger generations. The present study aims to explore the generational differences between the adolescent students and their parents on intra-personal management and its implications and recommendations in furtherance as there is imminent need to address their emotional imbalance, instant gratification, oppressive thoughts, weak adaptability, swaying moods, and such other issues that germane to the human inner life. The current study sample is comprised of 483 adolescent students and their parents numbering 422 through random sampling for the experimental study from Andhra Pradesh, India. The Intrapersonal management inventory had been re-adopted from Emotional intelligence Inventory of Mangal and Mangal (2015). The statistical parametric measures of Means, S.d's, 't'- values and 'p'- values were used to analyse the results. The results of the study revealed that there is significant variance in the intrapersonal management between one generation (students) to the yester generation (parents) with t-value of 6.452 at p-value of 0.000 and the students low intrapersonal management score as against their counter group warrants interventional strategies for the corrective action to step-up the intrapersonal management skills of the adolescents.

Keywords:- *Intrapersonal Management, Generation Gap, Soft Skills, Adolescents.*

I. INTRODUCTION

For any Nation to progress and flourish an individual's all-round development in personality is very important. Personality is a complex construct and is a combination of talents, abilities, attitudes, values, hopes that make an individual a unique person, especially the adolescent period, is the basis for it. Adolescence is crucial and critical, characteristically an important phase in the life span of an individual in which time majority of personality cult would

be acquired for their success in life. But due to the generational rift and conflict, have incessantly been there in the society with sharp disagreements across generations characterising one, the youth as a stubborn and rebellious with identity problem and the other, the parents as a very obstinate generation with no faith in children (Tom William Smith, 2000) exerting an ineradicable influence on them, causing detraction from their blooming, have attracted the imminent and immediate need for the intervention from the appropriate incumbents in scaffolding the youth. Generation gap, a quiet revolution, is considered as the difference between personal choices, beliefs, opinions and perceptions of different generations which lead to conflicts and concerns between the social dyads. This problem is often viewed as generational conflict, reminiscent of 1960's when a generation gap was first noticed, and became part of popular culture. (Frank Giancola 2006) and is one of the clearest example of inter-group perceptions manifested by age. (Vern L Bengtson, 1971). The concept of generation gap is linked to the notion of non-overlapping and overlapping populations and it refers to the amount of overlap between parents and their children. (Jayshree sarma, Kenneth De Jong 2000). Serious analysis of generations started in 19th century, emerging from a growing awareness of the possibility of permanent social transition and the idea of youthful revolt against the established social order. The generation gaps are more on items in which the cohort effects enhance the life cycle effects and when social systems accentuate the natural differences pertained to aging and vice-versa. The key to bridge the span between the generations is learning to understand the point of view of each and respect their rifts through a series of different mechanisms that bring change among the social dyads.

The content and connotation of the phenomenon of intrapersonal management lead to clarify the concepts derived from the term intrapersonal intelligence which have their own specificity of subject areas that include the facets as Intrapersonal relations, intrapersonal understanding, and intrapersonal skills, all of which relate to such semantic category of intrapersonal potential (Barber, 2005, Gardner, 2011 and Perez & Ruz, 2014). Many intra-personal relations start with 'self' as they are needed to handle one's relationship with them and how well a person can deal with his/her thoughts, emotions, desires and anything that drives, motivates, or discourages him/her determines how refined his/her intrapersonal skills are. One should possess excellent soft skills too like emotional stability, self-

regulation, adaptability, delaying gratification, concentration, and resilience, to mention few, the attributes of intrapersonal management skills apart from the out spoken talents, leadership, team work, good verbal communication etc. of inter-personal relations to succeed in the present day's hectic competition. The present days youth generation's psychology is different from its previous generation in view of the way of raising children with limited personal relations due to the dwindling of extended family set-ups, protrusion of nuclear families, the parents busy schedule thereby can't cater or spend time with their children but coupled with pampering, diminishing the family cohesion which situation is totally different from the earlier ambiance, playing a pivotal role in widening the generation gap in intrapersonal management which obviously had its bearing on its detraction. Studying intrapersonal management as a source with relevance to generational differences become even more prominent when it comes to adolescents disabilities of the day since recently the issue related to the process of integration of children with various forms of vices have become significantly more important, this small endeavour had been initiated to rationalise and reduce the present day generational differences in intrapersonal management.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Though sizable researches were carried out on the subject of generation gap, like generation gap between youth and their parents (Samuel Lubell, 1968, Lillian E roll, 1972, Tom William Smith, 2000, Frank Giancola, 2006), work place generation gap (Minda Zeitlin, 1992, Stephanie Wood,2005, Simon and Schuster,2009,K.R. Subrahmanyam,2017), bridging the generation gap (Susan Moore Johnson&Susan M Kardos, 2005, Linda Gravett, 2007, Stella Ress, 2010, Eve Sprunt et al, 2012), digital generation gap (Edna Aphek, 2001, Jane Kolodinsky et al, 2002, Lynn Schofield Clark, 2009, J Mitchell Vaterlaus, 2012), and gender generation gap (Mary Zey-Ferrell et al, 1978, Pippa Norris, 1993 & 1999, David De Vaus, 1997), etc., the literature is replete with research in to the subject of generation gap on psycho-emotional attributes like intrapersonal management skills and the like. The prominent impression left by the term generation gap is that of united young blood that is breaking drastically from both its elders and society in almost every perceivable manner. (Samuel Lubell, 1968), despite this, very few thorough studies have been yet made to illuminate the nature and extent of continuity or differences between the today's generations (Vern L Bengtson, 1970). Generation gap occurs due to the disparity in ages, genders, cultures and races that create various values and attitudes to same matter (Choong Yong, RashadYazdanifard, 2013). But generational differences while always there, it does not appear to be constant in intensity and impact, but seems to wax and wane across time. (Tom William Smith, 2000).The generational disparities between youth and elders in contemporary American society reflects a real and serious conflict of interest rather than mutual misunderstanding. (Edgar Z Friedenberg, 1969). There is high degree of disagreement between how emerging youth and their parents view their

relationship, as parents are more likely to expect high relationship quality while children aspire for greater contact and assistance exchanges (Adam Shapiro, 2004). In one of the studies it is revealed that the generation gap is viewed as a paradox as the young people are challenging elders that they are ready to jump across the gap to the other side of adulthood, where competence, independence, autonomy, self-confidence reside (Brian J McVeigh,2004) and the present day people of four different generations are being asked to work together challenging the influence of generation gap as HR issue proving as reasons to regard the generation gap as an idea that is more myth than reality (Frank Giancola,2006. In yet another studies the analysis of data disclosed that both the generations were facing difficulties in understanding one another and the gap can be spanned by way of discussions, good communication, understanding and spending time with each other (Mehak Aggarwal et al. 2017)

Intrapersonal management is the ability to read one's self, judging one's strengths and weaknesses, recognising and controlling emotions, and the talent to resolve conflicts in many issues for bringing psychological balance (Perez & Ruz, 2011) and it is also the capacity to control and regulate one's own feelings, emotions and attitudes related to self (Barber 2005). While the intrapersonal area represents an individual's subjective psychological functioning, the interpersonal domain denotes an individual's social functioning. (Dufner et al. 2017) which difference is empirically substantiated by factor and profile analysis (e.g., Gilman and Anderman 2006: Park et al. 2017). Children's intra and interpersonal domains develop throughout their youth, but the prominence of these skills become particularly pronounced in adolescence when they consolidate their own identity and peer relationships that are referred to by other terms including life skills, character skills, social virtues, soft skills and emotional learning competencies, developmental assets, learning mind-sets and non- cognitive skills-character strengths have long been considered a necessary aspect of healthy human development (Aristotle, 1925:Daman, 1997: Duckworth & Yeager, 2005: Kamenetz, 2015: Lerner et al., 2005)). The attribute most relevant to self-regulation, a prime constituent of intrapersonal management, is conscientiousness which generally concerns the way the people manage their behaviour and the individuals who are high in such qualia tend to be confident, planful, disciplined and orderly (Costa and McCrae, 1992) In a study of American Indian Elders' resilience, a source of strength for building healthy future for youth, the outcomes of literature search coupled with the research study revealed that resilience, a prime component of intrapersonal skills, is exemplified in elders' lives and it's strategies are linked to cultural values, education, teaching and youth activities (Carmella B Kahn et al, 2016) and the children's dietary control was influenced by their self-efficacy, knowledge and use of health information where as in adults it was influenced by their self-efficacy, knowledge and discussion between adults and children and adult's intrapersonal determinants of dietary behaviour predicted corresponding children's measures (Rajiv N Rimal, 2003).

III. METHODOLOGY

The table 1 given below shows the descriptive statistics of the respondent subjects, the students and their parents, along with the details of coverage of area and the institutions.

Table 1: The descriptive statistics of the respondent subjects

S.no	Sample details	Total no.	Districts covered	Place of institutions: High schools/ Plus 2/ Degree colleges
1	Students (13—19) Years	483	Tirupati, Chittoor, Nellore, Prakasam, Bapatla, Kadapa and Rayachoti. (7 Districts)	*Venkatagiri, Chittoor, Nellore, L.N.Puram, Piler, and Madanapalli.(6) **Gudur, Punganur, Podalakur, Pamur and Rayachoti.(5)
2	Parents (43—49) Years	422		@Kavali, Addanki, Kadapa, Badvel and Proddatur (5) Total: 16 institutions

*High Schools, **Plus 2, @Degree colleges

➤ Study Sample

The present study is a survey based quantitative one to assess the generational differences on intrapersonal management. The sample for the current study is selected through random sampling technique comprised of 483 teen age students from government and private high schools and colleges with age group of 13 to 19 years and 422 parents of age group of 43 to 49 years from seven districts of Andhra Pradesh, India, the details of which are given in table 1 for instant view and reference. Care had been taken to cover the whole district evenly by selecting the schools/colleges from Mandal, Division and District headquarters so as to have homogeneously distributed sample.

➤ Tools Used

One out of the four areas i.e. intrapersonal management scale from the standard Emotional Intelligence Inventory by Mangal and Mangal (2015) comprising of 25

questions with three point alternative responses as Always, Some times and Never, was administered to the respondent subjects separately for students and their parents. The reliability coefficients of the inventory examined through three different methods were found to be; split half method: 0.89, K-R formula (20): 0.90, and test-retest method: 0.92.

➤ Data Collection Procedure

While collecting the data all the ethical code was followed by obtaining consent from the subjects and told that confidentiality of the data collected would be maintained etc., have been followed. The institute authorities and the students have been informed well in advance about the objectives of the study and they were explained in detail the instructions that there are no right or wrong answers, further requested to answer honestly and appropriately without any hesitation.

IV. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 2: Means, SD's, t- Value of intrapersonal management between the generations

Source	N	Mean	S.D	t- value	Significant level
Parents	422	32.31	8.17	6.452	0.01
Students	483	29.39	5.33		

The data was summarised in table 2 above with quantitative measures expressed as means; s.d.s, t-values to examine and measure the variances and analyse the influence of the generation gap on intrapersonal management. To test the mean variances and significant level between the independent groups, Student's t- test was used. The above results indicate that there is clear variance in means of the teens (29.39) and their parents (32.31) with t- value of 6.45 which clearly speaks that there is statistically significant difference in intrapersonal management between the teens and their parents and is endorsed by the previous study that the findings of the data identified ten soft skills, in other wards the intrapersonal skills that are missing and needed to STEM undergraduates for the next five years with leadership and human-connection as prioritised in the list and the results show that the soft skill gap in present STEM

undergraduates is significant and steadily increasing (Haleh Karimi, Anthony Pina, 2021). The low scores recorded in the means of the teens over the parents on intrapersonal management skills affirm that the upcoming generation is weak in self-regulation, adaptive capacity, introspection, and delay in gratification etc., the chief constituents of intrapersonal management skills which is substantiated from the present day youth's attitudes and tendencies such as eating dessert even when they have to lose weight, alcohol and drug dependency, unable to adopt to the situations till they are fulfilled, no introspection for their faults etc. to mention few. This may be due to the fact that present generation had more access to the basic resources and opportunities for their luxury life and pampering by parents, their busy life and withering of joint family setup resulting in failing to cope to keep in track their

intrapersonal skills when compared to the previous generations.

V. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study has uncovered few paramount results that have implications for both the parents group and the academicians to take stock of the situation and to provide congenial atmosphere to the children cope to enhance their intrapersonal management skills for their better future. This study demonstrated that the ingredients of intrapersonal management skills had their role for the resolution of so many problems encountering in the life span of an individual especially the adolescents. Moreover the lag in the personal touch and cohesiveness in the present day parent child relationship is becoming a cause in widening the generation gap. Further research is warranted to enhance the area. The current study expands all together a new horizon as there are no researches covering together the concepts of generation gap and the intrapersonal management though there are extensive studies on individual subjects and this exploration would act as a compass for future evaluation, goal setting and collaborative intervention from the concerned. Further this study has implications for the educational authorities to integrate intrapersonal management skills as part of their curriculum in the schools and colleges and provide interventional counselling/training programmes to parents and their children so as to promote and inject intrapersonal management skills to the young blood of the Nation.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

From the discussion of results it can be concluded as: the younger generation is low on intrapersonal management skills compared to their parental generation and generation gap persists on intrapersonal management skills.

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